

D2.1

User requirements and DAFNE+ architecture

Revision v1.0

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the co-creation methodology that DAFNE+ adopted to collect the user requirements (in the framework of T2.1) and reports the activities carried out in this direction. The outcome of this process is the prioritised list of user requirements which is provided in this document. Based on the user requirements, a list of system requirements was produced which has driven the design of the DAFNE+ architecture. The high-level specifications of this architecture are also provided here and will guide the development of the components of the DAFNE+ platform under WP3-4.

Keywords

User requirements, DAFNE+ architecture, co-creation workshops

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DAO	Decentralised Autonomous Organisation
DoA	Description of Action
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FL	Federated Learning
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IPFS	InterPlanetary File System
MoSCoW	Must, Should, Could, Will not have
NN	Neural Network
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience

1 Executive summary

DAFNE+ organized workshops with the different types of the end users of the platform to communicate the DAFNE+ vision and to gather input on diverse aspects of the platform. This feedback was collected through a mix of questionnaires, interviews and meetings - after the initial presentation of the DAFNE+ approach - to create a thorough understanding of what the users most need. This feedback was then turned into a list of user requirements which was: a) prioritized following the MoSCoW (Must, Should, Could, Will not have) approach and b) used to produce the system requirements (again adopting the MoSCoW approach). The next step was the design of the DAFNE+ architecture and the high-level specifications of the main components to drive the detailed design and development of the different components in WP3 and WP4.

The methodology and the outcomes of the process described above are presented in this deliverable. An update of this deliverable based on the outcomes of the development phase and of the validation/piloting phase will be prepared in M30.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and context of the document

This deliverable reports the activities and outcomes of tasks 2.1 and 2.2 during the first year of the project. In more detail, task 2.1 was focusing on the co-creation activities (i.e., the organisation of workshops during which user requirements were collected) and its main outcome was the list of user requirements. Task 2.2 has received this as input to produce the system requirement and finally the DAFNE+ architecture. The high-level architecture defined here will drive the technical developments in WP3 and WP4 towards delivering the first version of the DAFNE+ platform.

2.2 Document structure

The rest of this document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 3 describes the methodology, the process and the outcomes of task 2.1 and concludes with the list of the user requirements.
- Chapter 4 presents the system requirements.
- Chapter 5 provides a high-level view of the DAFNE+ platform architecture.
- Chapter 6 concludes this deliverable.

Additionally, the questionnaire used to collect the user requirements is included in the Appendix.

2.3 Dependencies to/from other WPs

This deliverable does not depend on any other deliverable or WP (apart from the DoA). It provides valuable information to:

- WP3 for the design and development of specific components like the creative tools and the recommendation engine
- WP4 for the design and development of the platform and the support of NFTs
- WP6 for the definition of novel business models of interest to the public, IPR issues, legal and monetisation aspects.
- WP7 (partially) for the identification of the interest of the DAFNE+ target groups.

3 User requirements

In this chapter we present the activities undertaken in the framework of task 2.1 towards the collection of the DAFNE+ user requirements.

3.1 Requirement collection methodology

The methodology for the collection of the user requirements is depicted in Figure 1. It clearly shows a strong collaboration a) among the technical and use-case partners of the consortium and b) with end users outside the project team.

The first phase was devoted to a bottom-up process involving all consortium partners in several internal workshops to identify the main pieces of information to be obtained. The process combined:

- The production by use case leaders of storylines associated with each use case and defining the target users, their roles in relation to the assets to be managed in the blockchain platform and their expectations and motivations for the proposed services to be elicited.
- The production by technical, business and legal partners of a set of general questions that cut across the various use cases.

This process resulted in an initial set of questions, which were then processed again to streamline them to produce the questionnaire.

FIGURE 1: THE DAFNE+ METHODOLOGY FOR USER REQUIREMENTS COLLECTION

The dissemination leader and use case leaders drew up an action plan aimed at reaching the target users in each use case community and obtaining feedback from them by various means, including the organization of workshops and interviews. The questionnaire resulting from the previous phase often served as the basis for these sessions with users, enabling individual or collective exchanges on the issues it raised with them, as well as feedback from them to improve it, for example by reformulating certain questions.

This process culminated in a final version of the questionnaire implemented as an online survey, which was publicly announced through various communication channels (project website, consortium partner and parent project websites -including STARTS-, e-mailings and social networks).

Use case managers gathered qualitative feedback from these oral exchanges with representatives of their communities. In parallel with the launch of the survey, they compiled them in written form to complement and help interpret the survey responses to feed into the platform specification. Another function of this

production, presented in more detail as user scenarios in deliverable D2.2, was to develop refined versions of the use case specifications as part of task T2.3.

3.2 Requirement collection tools

The requirements were collected through questionnaires, interviews and workshops as described in the following sections.

3.2.1 Online surveys (questionnaires)

To create the questionnaires that would be addressed to the end-users during the co-creation activities, each partner was prompted to add questions relevant to the functionality or the topic they are designing in the project and for which they feel in need of user guidance. This resulted in more than 100 questions, which were then processed towards reducing them as it is not feasible to pose so many questions to external users. Additionally, towards addressing the appropriate questions to the appropriate end users, we used the answers provided to make available to them only relevant questions (i.e., to avoid asking somebody about music processing tools, if they are interested in other types of artifacts).

The link offered to the users was: <https://forms.office.com/r/r2be31USZm>

The full list of questions can be found in the appendix and for each question an Identifier has been provided, which will be used to associate the user requirements with the asked questions (for traceability purposes).

The online survey was answered by 82 people. The following demographic statistics were extracted:

- The majority of the users are active in arts and design, the second largest group are engineers and developers, and the third belongs to the academic field. The complete distribution regarding the fields in which the users are active can be seen in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: USERS' ACTIVITY

- Regarding the level of professionalism of the users asked, the largest portion are professionals and experts, with very few reporting “little to no experience in their fields”.

FIGURE 3: USERS' LEVEL OF PROFESSIONALISM

- The five most common creative areas of expertise of the users are the following, listed in order of popularity:
 - Music and Sound
 - Media Arts
 - Performing Arts
 - Installations
 - Design

FIGURE 4: USERS' CREATIVE AREAS OF EXPERTISE

- Most users have no experience or no knowledge regarding blockchain technologies, and only a few have experience in using them. The same pattern emerged when the users were asked about their familiarity with NFTs.

FIGURE 5: USERS' FAMILIARITY WITH BLOCKCHAIN

3.2.2 Interviews

The interviews organised by use-case leaders with expert representatives of their communities were an important aspect of the user feedback process: they enabled us to test initial ideas and to collect qualitative feedback complementary to the answers provided in the survey.

For Use-case 1, MMU conducted interviews with students and staff in MMU to facilitate qualitative discussion on the underpinning principles of DAFNE+ and artistic applications for the user group. The questions asked to the participants were taken from the main survey based on applicability and relevance to the selected group. The approach was semi-structured in this fashion with these initial questions leading to further discussion and follow up questions that gave the researchers insight into the needs and requirements of users who are interested in using the platform. The format also suited the stage of development of DAFNE+ in that users were not educated on its purposes or on the field of blockchain and NFTs in general. They were able to be expansive and ideate on possible benefits and features for the use case whilst in design phase.

Along with our internal university audience, we also engaged with MMU industry stakeholders, including the BBC, and North West Film Archive – a heritage archive organisation. Whilst these discussions were also structured using key questions from the questionnaire, resulting discussion was focused on their own requirements for these types of systems and their institutional experience of engaging with users in situations with complex rights agreements and novel creative applications of technology.

For Use-case 2, IRCAM conducted 1,5-to-2-hour long interviews with 12 experts of the computer music field, mostly artists and computer music designers not familiar with blockchains and NFTs and a few experts of the field. The general objective was to enable in-depth exchanges based on the initial storylines, get feedback on the interest they may raise, on conditions of success to consider, but also to let new ideas emerge, to feed refined use-case specifications. The interviews were conducted as a free exchange and brainstorm based on a limited number of high-level questions, after a short introduction on the project's objectives. The goal was also to motivate a first circle of high-level users.

For Use-case 3, IAAC conducted eight one-on-one interviews, lasting an hour each, with profiles from the Distributed Design Platform network (Creative Talents and Partners) and external content creators during the survey fill-out. The objective was to gain subjective insights into the platform's concept and vision while

comprehending the survey's critical steps. Additionally, this conversation format enabled a stronger relationship with network members.

3.2.3 Workshops

The purpose of workshops organised by Use-case leaders was to raise awareness on the project and present it in the framework of public and private events, support the completion of the online survey and get feedback to support the specification process.

The list of organised events during the specification phase is presented in Table 1:

Event name	Type	Date	Place	Resp. partner	Use - case	Nr of attendees	Categories of attendees	Link
IRCAM Forum workshops NYC	Workshop, hybrid presence + zoom	30/9/22	New York University, USA	IRCAM	2	32	University student and Faculty in music technologies, music and sound artists	[6]
Fab Lab Barcelona - internal workshop	Workshop	30/9/22	Barcelona	IAAC	3	5		
Maker Faire Rome	Maker Faire	6-9/10/2022	Rome	IAAC	3	40.000 (general outreach)	Makers, Designers, General Public (Families)	[7]
Fab Fest	Festival	12-22/10/2022	Bali	IAAC	3	~200		[7]
IRCAM plenary meeting	Internal staff meeting	17/10/22	Paris	IRCAM	2	70	Researchers, engineers, curators,	

							producers, admin	
IRCAM Directors meeting	Internal executive meeting	18/10/22	Paris	IRCAM	2	10	Departmen t directors	
Kiel : Interdisciplina rie wochen	Workshop	3/11/22	Kiel, Germany	IRCAM	2	7	Engineers, creative, Media industry and academics	[9]
SODA staff workshop	Workshop	15/11/22	Manchest er	SODA	1, 2	6	Staff, practitione r	
IRCAM Forum webinar	Webinar	16/11/22	online	IRCAM	2		IRCAM Forum Members	[10]
SODA and the North West Film Archive	Workshop	30/11/22	Manchest er	SODA	1	2		
SODA music and sound students workshop	Taught session	30/11/22	Manchest er	SODA	2		Students	
SODA NFT Group Meeting	Workshop	16/11/22	Manchest er	SODA	1		Practitione rs, collectors	
SODA External Partners Meeting A (Music)	Networkin g event	30/11/22	Manchest er	SODA	2		Senior technical and creative executives	
HfMT Workshop	Workshop	5/12/22	Hamburg, Germany	IRCAM	2	6	HfMT MultiMedia Departmen t Staff and Students	emai l.

SODA Future Media Production (FMP) Workshop	Taught session	8/12/22	Manchester	SODA	1	15	Students	
MediaFutures Workshop	Presentation during private event	9/12/22	online	IRCAM	2	32	Media Futures EU program artists and startups	[11]
SODA External Partners Meeting B (Prosumer)	Networking event	9/12/22	Manchester	SODA	2		Senior technical and creative executives	
Blockchain & Digital Commons at Espacio Open	Workshop	16/12/22	Spain, Bilbao	IAAC	3	9	Designers, Artists, Makers, Architects	[12]
DAFNE+ presentation	Conference	30/3/23	Paris	IRCAM	2	50	Music and sound professionals and students	[13]
DAFNE+ Workshop	Workshop	31/3/23	Paris	FCF, IRCAM	2	12	Music and sound professionals and students	[14]

TABLE 1: THE EVENTS ORGANISED TOWARDS USER REQUIREMENTS' COLLECTION

3.3 User requirements list adopting the MoSCoW prioritization methodology

Based on the responses to the questionnaires and the feedback from the workshops, the following list of requirements has been produced.

Requirement ID	User requirement description	MoSCoW	Nm. Of Question on the Questionnaire
UR1	The user could be able to import the assets created by DAFNE+ automatic creation tools on 3rd-party software.	Could have	C6_Q1
UR2	The user should be able to create content for music compositions, video illustrations, paintings or games/apps.	Should have	C3_Q7
UR3	The user should be provided with tools for automatic content creation.	Should have	C3_Q8
UR4	The user should be able to fully customize a virtual avatar using an image of its face and body parameters.	Should have	C3_Q1
UR5	The user should be able to automatically produce artworks by transforming existing images or creating new ones.	Should have	C3_Q1
UR6	The user should be able to extract motion sequences and body model parameters from video sequences.	Should have	C3_Q1
UR7	The user should be able to reconstruct 3D models from one or more images of a 2D object.	Should have	C3_Q1
UR8	The user must be able to import its face to a virtual avatar.	Must have	C3_Q2
UR9	The user should be able to modify the avatar's body parameters, clothes and skin tone.	Should have	C3_Q2
UR10	The user must be able to extract full body motion data from video sequences.	Must have	C3_Q3
UR11	The user must be able to transform 2D objects, characters or animals from images to 3D models.	Must have	C3_Q4
UR12	The user should be able to transform or generate artistic images of Cubism, Hyperrealism, Impressionism, Surrealism, Expressionism styles.	Should have	C3_Q5

UR13	The user could be able to transform or generate artistic images of Abstraction and American Comic styles.	Could have	C3_Q5
UR14	The user must find is easy to use and create components	Should have	C0_Q6
UR15	The user should find it easy to create repositories	Should have	C0_Q6
UR16	The user could easily create and develop components	Could have	C0_Q6
UR17	The user will not need assistance in the maintenance and update of existing repositories	Will not have	C0_Q6
UR18	The user will not need assistance in the the collection of repositories and the buying of technical setups for artworks	Will not have	C0_Q6
UR19	The user must be able to see the pricing (transparency) and the fairness of the prices should be easily perceived (fairness)	Must have	C5.1_Q9
UR20	The user should be able to share their published content on the main social media, video, audio and software platforms.	Should have	C5.1_Q9
UR21	The user should be able to choose licenses to release their content.	Should have	C5.1_Q9
UR22	The user should be able to find the best quality content in the platform, seeing first the best content on general views or specific searches.	Should have	C5.1_Q9
UR23	The user should be presented with explanatory content relevant to the technology.	Should have	C5.1_Q9
UR24	The users should receive (be presented with) explanations of technical terms and technical info related to blockchain should be provided	Should have	C5.1_Q9
UR25	The users should be presented with explanations the role and the benefits stemming from NFTs.	Should have	C5_Q11
UR26	The user should be able to list NFTs created on DAFNE+ to the OpenSea external marketplace.	Should have	C5_Q9
UR27	The users should be provided with brief explanations regarding DAOs.	Should have	C8_Q07, C8_Q04, C8_Q08, C8_Q13,

			C8_Q09, C5.2_Qx (B28)
UR28	The users should be provided with a simple and clear method to become members of DAOs and participate in the making of decisions.	Should have	C8_Q07, C8_Q04, C8_Q08, C8_Q13, C8_Q09, C5.2_Qx (B28)
UR29	The users should be provided with clear incentives to participate in the DAOs.	Should have	C8_Q07, C8_Q04, C8_Q08, C8_Q13, C8_Q09, C5.2_Qx (B28)
UR30	The users will not need to collaborate with an external DAO.	Will not have	Part of C5_Q14
UR31	The user must have the possibility to work with audio files	Must have	C5.1_Q1
UR32	The user must have the possibility to work with video files.	Must have	C5.1_Q1
UR33	The user must have the possibility to work with image files.	Must have	C5.1_Q1
UR34	The user could have the possibility to work with 3D media files.	Could have	C5.1_Q1
UR35	The user could have the possibility to connect with their social networks through the platform.	Could have	C5.1_Q3
UR36	The user must have the possibility to track authorship of a final asset.	Must have	C5.1_Q4
UR37	The user should have the possibility to co-create the digital asset.	Should have	C5.1_Q6
UR38	The user could have the possibility to add, view, and edit work on any device.	Could have	C5.1_Q7
UR39	The user must view their digital assets.	Must have	C5.1_Q7

UR40	The user should have the possibility to communicate inside the platform.	Should have	C5.1_Q10
UR41	The users must be able to add tags to define their profession, level of expertise and area of interest, connection to DAO's (Example: https://electronics.stackexchange.com/users/160807/eduardo-cardoso)	Must have	C5.3_Q2
UR42	The user must have the ability to create teams, organisation and projects.	Must have	C5.3_Q4
UR43	The users must have the ability to have relations between teams, organisation and projects with different roles and permissions. (Reviewer, contributor, promoter, viewer)	Must have	C5.3_Q4
UR44	The user must be able to use a file picker that provides visualisation and feedback to what is being uploaded with the option to add visualisers for 3D files or highlight code. (Example GitHub: https://github.com/rwaldron/johnny-five)	Must have	C5.3_Q5
UR45	The user must be able to access the DAFNE+ Platform as a web application. (i.e., using browser)	Must have	C1_Q2
UR46	The user should be able to access the DAFNE+ platform via mobile phone.	Should have	C1_Q2
UR47	The user could be able to install some of the tools of the DAFNE+ in its own environment. (i.e., laptop)	Could have	C1_Q2
UR48	The user should be able to integrate external systems in DAFNE+ using APIs.	Should have	C1_Q2
UR49	The users must be able to directly import artefacts into 3rd-party software.	Must have	C5_Q7
UR50	The user could be able to use widgets of DAFNE+ content.	Could have	C5_Q7
UR51	The user could be able to share DAFNE+ content on social media.	Could have	C5_Q7
UR52	The user must be able to a navigate the DAFNE+ platform in a secure way.	Must have	C1_Q4
UR53	The user should have an easy and confident approach with the usage of the DAFNE+ platform.	Should have	C1_Q4

UR54	The user should be able to access the DAFNE+ with different mechanisms.	Should have	C1_Q3
UR55	The user should be able to access the DAFNE+ platform in a secure way.	Should have	C1_Q3
UR56	The user should get personalized content recommendations on the DAFNE+ platform.	Should have	C4_Q1
UR57	The user should receive content recommendations based on its profile.	Should have	C4_Q2
UR58	The user could receive content recommendations based on the preferences of similar users or popular content.	Could have	C4_Q2
UR59	The user should be able to manually correct keywords proposed by the DAFNE+ content analysis algorithm.	Should have	C4_Q3
UR60	The user should receive clear and simple instructions on how to create a Web3 wallet.	Should have	C5_Q15
UR61	The user should be supported to use MetaMask as the Web3 identity provider.	Should have	Part of C5_Q15
UR62	The users must be supported/allowed to mint of tokens in the Ethereum network.	Must have	C5_Q12
UR63	The users should be supported/allowed to mint of tokens in the Polygon network.	Should have	C5_Q12
UR64	The users could be supported/allowed to mint of tokens in the Solana network.	Could have	C5_Q12
UR65	The user must be able to view basic information regarding the blockchain operations taking place on the platform. (e.g. using block explorers)	Must have	C5_Q5
UR66	The user must be able to make transactions with fairly low costs using DAFNE+.	Must have	C5_Q6
UR67	The user should be able to make quick transactions.	Must have	C5_Q6
UR68	The user must feel that the offered blockchain functionality is secure.	Must have	C5_Q6
UR69	For the user, it is important that the DAFNE+ platform as well as the tools used to create it are open source.	Should have	C5_Q6

UR70	The user should be provided with a highly decentralized blockchain infrastructure.	Should have	C5_Q6
UR71	The user could be provided with a low energy consumption mechanism for the blockchain interactions performed on DAFNE+.	Could have	C5_Q6
UR72	The user could be able to interconnect their DAFNE+ assets with other platforms (platform interoperability).	Could have	C5_Q6
UR73	The users are not interested in DAFNE+ being compatible with other external marketplaces.	Will not have	C5_Q6
UR74	The user should be able to update/upgrade NFTs.	Should have	C5_Q7
UR75	The user could be able to create time limited NFTs.	Could have	C5_Q7
UR76	The user will not be able to create non-hashable NFTs.	Will not have	C5_Q7
UR77	The user must be provided with well-documented and user-friendly APIs for the usage of DAFNE+ tools.	Must have	C6_Q2
UR78	The user must be provided with API documentation built on open-source solutions.	Must have	C6_Q2
UR79	The user should be able to easily read and comprehend the API documentation.	Should have	C6_Q2
UR80	The user will not need an API Documentation with an aesthetically well-design UI.	Will not have	C6_Q2
UR82	If DAFNE+ is to provide an API documentation tool, this should be either Swagger or Postman.	Should have	C6_Q4

TABLE 2: THE USER REQUIREMENTS OF DAFNE+ PLATFORM

Apart from the above user requirement, the responses to the questionnaire led us to a set of valuable observations which have been taken into consideration during the architecture design. These are:

1. The users are expected to use their tools in their working environment.
2. No major preference to a specific software from the user side was observed.
3. Most respondents were self-employed users (40%) and employed (25%), followed by 12% of Artistic commissions and 10% academics. The platform should not assume selling content or licenses is the main source (or even a significant portion) of the income for the great majority of users.
4. There is a diversity of platforms where users publish their work. Main types are repositories, both public/open or private, as well as social media.

5. 44% of the respondents sell their components and repositories as the outcome of a service and 41% exploit their components and repositories in other ways (more research needed)
6. Key motives for using a platform are: 1) Payments and incentives, 2) redistribution and basic income, 3) Audience and community building, 4) Licensing, and 5) Fairness and transparency as the key important things to change in how creative work is rewarded.
7. Only 26% know what NFTs are, and most of the users do not know what NFTs are or have only heard of the term.
8. 30% of the respondents use OpenSea. 12% have used Tezos -enabled OBJKT. No other marketplace has been used by a remarkable portion of the respondents.
9. Users rely on blockchain and the purported "immutability" to track authorship and originality. Notification systems for similar or blatant copies of works, that let the original user know would be optimal, but entail major resources. Copyright infringement notification procedures need to be discussed further on.
10. None of the users has experience with DAOs or is a member of one.
11. 53% of the respondents were interested in the professional sound and music production, 31% interested in art, design, making and fashion and 17% in non-professional content production.
12. Collaborative versioning seems to be a necessity to face the technological obsolescence due to OS type environments. Also, the collaborative aspect allows the eruption of novelty. Finally, a formal description of the functionalities can improve the long-term durability.
13. The versioning system plays in favour of the sustainability of the repositories, and thus of the platform. Not yet adopted by the users, the virtues seem nevertheless appreciated and valued.
14. Depending on which activity one would do, versioning would play a bigger or smaller role. For example, in coding versioning is quite common and plays an important role. In relation to hardware its less common, but just as relevant. However, versioning in hardware is still less explored. The definition of what a "version" is, is needed, to understand the traceability of steps.
15. Contents and security have the overall higher rank in the questionnaire even if security has a high number of low scores (1 for approx. 30%). UX has a high overall rank among the users. Performance and cross-platform usage are not so relevant.

4 System requirements

After eliciting the user requirements, the next step was the definition of the system requirements. While user requirements define the results and the functionalities the user wants, the system requirements define what the system must do to achieve this.

The user requirements have the following characteristics:

- Written for users
- Natural Language
- No technical details

The system requirements are instead more oriented to the technical implementation:

- Written for developers
- Technical Language
- Detailed Functional and Non-Functional requirements

Each user requirement was analysed and one or more system requirements were defined. In addition, some user requirements were mapped in more than one system requirement, due to their complexity.

At the end, the system requirements were grouped by functionality and mapped with the most relevant component of the DAFNE+ Architecture (see Chapter 5 for additional information about the different components), even though the implementation of a requirement in most cases involves the collaboration of more than one component. Table 3 below reports the final list of system requirements.

System Requirement ID	User Requirement IDs	System Requirement Description	MoSCoW	Relevant component
Identity Management				
SYS_IM_1	C5.3._Q2	The platform must allow the users to add tags to define their profession, level of expertise and area of interest, connection to DAO's on their profiles.	Must have	Identity and Profile Management
SYS_IM_2	C5.3_Q4	The platform must support users to create teams, organisations, and projects.	Must have	Identity and Profile Management
SYS_IM_3	C5.3_Q4	The platform must support the creation of roles and permission rules for teams, organisations, and projects.	Must have	Identity and Profile Management
SYS_IM_4	C1_Q4, C1_Q3	DAFNE+ must support security access (e.g., TLS, OAuth, etc.)	Must have	Identity and Profile Management

SYS_IM_5	C1_Q3	DAFNE+ platform must support login with user credentials (username and password).	Must have	Identity and Profile Management
SYS_IM_6	C1_Q3	DAFNE+ could support two-factor authentication.	Could have	Identity and Profile Management
SYS_IM_7	C1_Q3	DAFNE+ could support 3rd-party login. (e.g., a social network login)	Could have	Identity and Profile Management
SYS_IM_8	C5_Q15	DAFNE+ must use MetaMask as the Web3 identity provider.	Must have	Blockchain and NFT service
Rights, Remuneration and Licensing				
SYS_REM_1	C7_Q1, C7_Q2, C7_Q5, C5.2_Qx (B5, B6)	The platform should have clear remuneration schematics based on distribution of profit: this entails a) correct crediting; b) functioning wallet connections; c) price structures that are transparent.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_2	C7_Q10	DAFNE+ platform should enable: a) easy ways to get rewards and incentives from published content, b) economic models that are redistributive and offer some type of basic income.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_3	C8_Q07, C8_Q04, C8_Q08, C8_Q13, C8_Q09, C5.2_Qx (B28)	The platform should allow the author to choose to enable free resale or return on resale. This is driven as an imposition on the user that resells the asset. The platform should also natively include this function as default on the user side but it can be turned off.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_4	C8_Q07, C8_Q04, C8_Q08, C8_Q13, C8_Q09, C5.2_Qx (B28)	The platform should allow the user to choose the layering of rights that they want to grant a user after making an asset available, including making it available for a fee, and having a function not dissimilar to "buy the author a coffee" for tipping structures without user obligation.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_5	C8_Q12	The platform should "sell assets" through "proprietary digital property" agreements.	Should have	Content Management

SYS_REM_6	C8_Q12	The platform should have an option to acquire the rights to assets, libraries or works.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_7	C8_Q12	The platform should support the author/publisher to set which rights they are willing to grant and at which price	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_8	C8_Q12	The platform should support the user to comply with price structures, depending on what they want to acquire. A feature to "request a license" and send an inquiry to authors that have not made particular rights available to license out should also be present.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_9	C5.2_Q2	The platform should enable to manage a distribution of assets rights between several users and related monetization redistribution.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_REM_10	C5.1_Q9	The platform should have an easy way to choose licenses for the published content.	Should have	Content Management
Content Management				
SYS_CM_1	C5.3_Q5	The platform must allow the visualisation of content.	Must have	Content Management
SYS_CM_2	C5.3_Q5	The platform could provide specific visualisation feedback based on content type.	Could have	Content Management
SYS_CM_3	C2_Q3	The platform must allow to categorize the tools under different categories/tags mentioning the domains in the form of a list that can evolve in the future.	Must have	Content Management
SYS_CM_4	C5.2_Q5, C5.3_Q10	Asset production and management (including versioning) should be possible by an individual or by a group.	Should have	Content Management
SYS_CM_5	C5.2_Q5	The platform could provide collaborative features on tools.	Could have	Content Management

SYS_CM_6	C5.2._Q7	DAFNE+ should enable the provisioning of sufficient documentation for each asset - component and repository.	Must have	Content Management
SYS_CM_7	C5.2._Q7	DAFNE+ could support a moderation system based on peer-to-peer reviews that would promote better documented projects and thus encourage the quality of documentation indirectly/directly.	Could have	Content Management
SYS_CM_8	C5.1._Q9	The platform should allow the users to sort content based on the quality (e.g., most popular first).	Should have	NFT Marketplace
SYS_CM_9	C5.2._Q6	The platform must support a git-like technology for storing repositories with LFS (Large-File-Storage) for media files.	Must have	Git-like Management tool
SYS_CM_10	C5.2._Q8	The platform should support transactions between users for enabling the creation of a new version by a user in relation to users responsible for the creation of former versions.	Should have	Git-like Management tool
SYS_CM_11	C5.2._Q8	The platform should provide easy access to basic asset versioning features (create, version, download, contribute...). An expert mode should allow access to all relevant features.	Should have	Git-like Management tool
NFTs				
SYS_NFT_1	C5.1._Q7	DAFNE+ platform must have an UI to display NFTs.	Must have	NFT Marketplace
SYS_NFT_2	C5._Q9	DAFNE+ should integrate its DAFNE+ marketplace with OpenSea.	Should have	NFT Marketplace
SYS_NFT_3	C5.1._Q1	DAFNE+ platform must have the possibility to create NFTs with any type of file	Must have	NFT Tool
SYS_NFT_4	C5.1._Q4	DAFNE+ platform must make available the info of the authorship of any NFT.	Must have	NFT Tool
SYS_NFT_5	C5.1._Q6	DAFNE+ platform should have the possibility to share an NFT between multiple users.	Should have	NFT Tool

SYS_NFT_6	C5_Q7	DAFNE+ could support the creation of time-limited NFTs.	Could have	NFT Tool
SYS_NFT_7	C5_Q7	DAFNE+ should offer the ability to upgrade NFTs.	Should have	NFT Tool
Blockchain Realm				
SYS_BLC_1	C5_Q5	DAFNE+ must provide the users with basic information regarding the blockchain operations taking place on the platform.	Must have	Blockchain Realm
SYS_BLC_2	C5_Q6	DAFNE+ blockchain infrastructure must have low transaction costs, high speed and be secure.	Must have	Blockchain Realm
SYS_BLC_3	C5_Q6	DAFNE+ blockchain infrastructure should be based upon open-source technologies and be highly decentralized.	Should have	Blockchain Realm
SYS_BLC_4	C5_Q6	DAFNE+ blockchain infrastructure could use "greener" networks and offer interoperability features.	Could have	Blockchain Realm
SYS_BLC_5	C5_Q12	DAFNE+ must allow for the minting of tokens in the Ethereum network	Must have	Blockchain Realm
SYS_BLC_6	C5_Q12	DAFNE+ should allow for the minting of tokens in the Polygon network	Should have	Blockchain Realm
SYS_BLC_7	C5_Q12	DAFNE+ could allow for the minting of tokens in the Solana network	Could have	Blockchain Realm
DAOs				
SYS_DAO_1	C5_Q14	DAFNE+ should provide very simple and clear methods for users to become members of DAOs and participate in the making of decisions.	Should have	DAOs
SYS_DAO_2	C5_Q14	DAFNE+ should provide clear incentives for the users to participate in DAFNE+ DAOs.	Should have	DAOs
Platform Toolset				
SYS_TOOL_1	C2_Q5	The platform should enable the operation of web audio-based	Should have	WebPD

applications, even if most community tools run on separate computer applications.				
SYS_TOOL_2	C3_Q7	DAFNE+ should allow users to create content for music compositions, video illustrations, paintings, or games/apps.	Should have	DAFNE+ toolset
SYS_TOOL_3	C3_Q8	DAFNE+ should provide tools for automatic content creation.	Should have	DAFNE+ toolset
SYS_TOOL_4	C3_Q1	DAFNE+ should provide a virtual avatar customization tool.	Should have	Virtual Avatar Personalization
SYS_TOOL_5	C3_Q1	DAFNE+ should provide tools for the automatic generation and transformation of artworks from existing images.	Should have	Automatic Artwork Generator
SYS_TOOL_6	C3_Q1	DAFNE+ should provide tools for 3D human motion data extraction from video sequences.	Should have	3D Human Pose Estimation
SYS_TOOL_7	C3_Q1	DAFNE+ should provide tools for 3D object reconstruction from one or multiple images.	Should have	3D Object Reconstruction
SYS_TOOL_8	C3_Q2	The DAFNE+ virtual avatar customization tool should allow the importing of a user's face to a virtual avatar.	Should have	Virtual Avatar Personalization
SYS_TOOL_9	C3_Q2	The DAFNE+ virtual avatar customization tool should allow modifications to body parameters, clothes, or skin tone of a virtual avatar.	Should have	Virtual Avatar Personalization
SYS_TOOL_10	C3_Q3	DAFNE+ must allow the 3D modelling of full body motion data from video sequences.	Must have	3D Human Pose Estimation
SYS_TOOL_11	C3_Q4	DAFNE+ must allow the creation of 3D models from 2D objects depicted in images.	Must have	3D Object Reconstruction
SYS_TOOL_12	C3_Q5	DAFNE+ should transform input images to specific style or generate artistic images of different styles.	Should have	Style Transfer

SYS_TOOL_13	C5.2._Q3	The platform should manage assets enabling the execution of a generative process.	Should have	WebPD
SYS_TOOL_14	C4_Q1	The platform should provide personalized content recommendations to its users.	Should have	AI Recommendation Engine
SYS_TOOL_15	C4_Q2	The platform should provide content recommendations to a user based on its profile and/or preferences of similar users and/or popular content.	Should have	AI Recommendation Engine
UI				
SYS_UI_1	C1_Q2	DAFNE+ platform must be implemented as a web app.	Must have	UI/UX
SYS_UI_2	C1_Q2, C5.1._Q7	DAFNE+ platform should be available from mobile phone (e.g., responsive web app or a specific mobile app).	Should have	UI/UX
SYS_UI_3	C1_Q4	DAFNE+ platform should be responsive.	Should have	UI/UX
SYS_UI_4	C1_Q4	DAFNE+ should be accessible.	Should have	UI/UX
SYS_UI_5	None	DAFNE+ Platform Apps must have a common/harmonic UI	Must have	UI/UX
FAQ and Chat				
SYS_FC_1	C0_Q6	DAFNE+ should facilitate the usage and creation of components and repositories through pop-up messages or FAQs or wizards or guides or short videos.	Should have	FAQ
SYS_FC_2	C5_Q10	DAFNE+ should provide the users with explanatory content regarding blockchain technology.	Should have	FAQ
SYS_FC_3	C5_Q10	DAFNE+ should add explanations to technical terms and technical info provided related to blockchain.	Should have	FAQ
SYS_FC_4	C5_Q11	DAFNE+ should briefly explain NFTs to users.	Should have	FAQ

SYS_FC_5	C8_Q07, C8_Q04, C8_Q08, C8_Q13, C8_Q09, C5.2_Qx (B28)	The platform should provide guidance on copyright management infringements and relevant processes with special emphasis on public works, out-of-commerce etc.	Should have	FAQ
SYS_FC_6	C8_Q10, C8_Q02, C7_Q7	The platform should have a clear-cut direct FAQ section on rights management and the approach to copyright to inform users as well as the privacy policy.	Should have	FAQ
SYS_FC_7	C5_Q14	DAFNE+ should explain DAOs to users.	Should have	FAQ
SYS_FC_8	C5.1_Q7	DAFNE+ platform should feature a chat between users.	Should have	Chat
SYS_FC_9	C5_Q15	DAFNE+ should provide clear and simple instructions on how to create a web3 wallet.	Should have	FAQ
Integration				
SYS_INT_1	C6_Q1	DAFNE+ automatic creation tools could export assets in suitable formats for 3rd-party software.	Could have	Integration Layer
SYS_INT_2	C1_Q2	DAFNE+ platform should support the integration of the external system via APIs.	Should have	Integration Layer
SYS_INT_3	C5_Q7	DAFNE+ must facilitate the direct importing of artefacts into 3rd-party software.	Must have	Integration Layer
SYS_INT_4	C5_Q7	DAFNE+ could support the usage of widgets of the DAFNE+ content.	Could have	Integration Layer
SYS_INT_5	C6_Q2	DAFNE+ must create well-documented and user-friendly APIs using open-source tools.	Must have	Integration Layer
SYS_INT_6	C6_Q2	DAFNE+ APIs should be easily readable and comprehensible.	Should have	Integration Layer

SYS_INT_7	C6_Q4	DAFNE+ APIs should be provided using Swagger or Postman.	Must have	Integration Layer
SYS_INT_8	C5.3_Q6, C6_Q5, C5.1_Q3, C5_Q7	The platform should be interoperable with other publishing platforms adopting open web standards and implementing APIs such as social networks, audio and video platforms and software repositories.	Should have	Integration Layer
Storage				
SYS_STR_1	C2_Q2, C5.2_Q4	The system must support the management of assets/files of any type that can potentially be large.	Must have	Storage
SYS_STR_2		The system must support a distributed file system (e.g., IPFS)	Must have	Storage

TABLE 3: SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS OF THE DAFNE+ PLATFORM

5 DAFNE+ high level architecture

5.1 Methodology

The main goals of the task 2.2 were to design the DAFNE+ architecture based on the captured and prioritized user requirements after their translation to system requirements, as well as to specify the components and interfaces of the DAFNE+ platform.

This section presents the approach and methodology that was followed for pursuing these goals.

FIGURE 6: T2.2 METHODOLOGY

As described in Figure 6, the activity carried out for the design of DAFNE+ architecture is divided into 4 macro-phases:

1. User requirements definition and collection (conducted in T2.1)
2. Concept architecture definition and collection of the architectural component's description and technical specifications
3. System requirements definition and mapping
4. Design and representation of the DAFNE+ Architecture

5.2 Architecture

The DAFNE+ Platform aims to be a “collaborative content sharing platform for DAOs over blockchains, easing the participation of artists and creators in the business models generated thanks to DAFNE+ ecosystem”.

The elicitation of the user and system requirements, together with the technical specifications of the architectural components, conducted us to design a high-level DAFNE+ architecture that describes the DAFNE+ platform and toolset.

Figure 7 below reports from a visual perspective all the layers and components expected to be part of DAFNE+ ecosystem.

FIGURE 7: DAFNE+ ARCHITECTURE

The following sections describe in detail the different layers and the architectural components of the DAFNE+ Platform as well as the technical specifications of the DAFNE+ toolset.

5.2.1 Application Layer

The Application Layer is the top layer of the DAFNE+ Architecture and consists of several end-user applications, made available through the DAFNE+ Platform User Interface.

The list of the application includes:

- Supporting Applications (Chat and FAQ)
- DAO Section
- NFT Marketplace
- Content Management
- GIT Management
- Tools UIs
- Tools Catalogue

Each application is comprehensive of the backend part, which contains the business logic and the interfaces with the other layers and components of DAFNE+ platform, as well as the frontend part, which will provide easy access to the end-users.

The User Interface of the DAFNE+ Platform will be consistent for any application to create a harmonic ecosystem that facilitates the user experience.

The applications included in the Application Layer will be able to interact with the Blockchain Realm (DAO Section and NFT Marketplace), with the DAFNE+ toolset (Tools UI and Tools Catalogue) as well as with the Storage Layer, for the data management and storage and the Integration Layer, for external integrations.

In addition, the Identity and Profile Management tool will allow the secure access and profiling of the users, while the AI recommendation engine aims to provide tailored recommendations about media content to the users of the platform.

In the sections below, all the applications are described in detail.

5.2.1.1 Content Management

The Content Management application will implement a complete media asset management value chain: creation, management and distribution of the content.

Creation

The creation of digital media assets within the DAFNE+ platform is intended as the possibility to add and/or import new content in the DAFNE+ ecosystem. The possibility to add new content will be made available through import functionalities, supporting the most standard and relevant type of content, following the requirements expectations and needs.

Management

The management phase will cover all the useful processes for the usage and the enrichment of the content within the DAFNE+ platform. The end-user will have the possibility to:

- Search specific content (with filtering and ordering features)
- Tag and categorize content.
- Create technical documentation with some additional details about the content and how it could be used.
- Collaborate on management activities with other users.

Distribution

The Content Management application will cover several aspects related to the distribution of the content.

- Definition of **access and usage rights** for other users of DAFNE+ (most probably for those other than the creators of the asset).
- Identification and application of **pricing and licensing** for the usage of the content
- Application of **remuneration mechanisms in a redistributed way**

The entire **content workflow will be integrated to the Blockchain Realm** and specific smart contracts will be implemented for tracking the processes and for the application of remuneration mechanisms, ensuring a **fair and transparent distribution of the revenue** to all the contributors.

5.2.1.2 DAO Section

A Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) is **an organization** governed through smart contracts on a blockchain network. It allows participants to vote freely and to eliminate traditional forms of centralized governance.

The DAFNE+ Platform will support the creation and management of DAOs, in which the users can participate and perform key actions (voting, proposing, allocating funds, etc.). All the key actions will be available through the DAO UI and performed using blockchain technology, integrating the DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm and specific smart contracts for DAOs management.

FIGURE 8: DAO SECTION FUNCTIONAL SCHEMA

In addition, since it is a blockchain-based application, the DAO section needs an integration with web3 wallets for the authentication of the user. The web3 wallet connection will be provided by the overall DAFNE+ platform.

5.2.1.3 NFT Marketplace

The DAFNE+ marketplace at its core is the place where the users will be able to buy and sell assets under appropriate and transparent IPR licenses and revenue models. The assets supported can be of any type of multimedia content like images, videos, or audio files.

The component will also feature a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that will maintain the same look and feel as with the rest of the platform to facilitate an easy and seamless experience for the users. Below is a list of the possible functionalities provided:

- View the assets listed on the marketplace with the ability to:
 - Search for specific items
 - Sort them according to specific features
 - Apply filters.
- Add new items on the marketplace as NFTs.
- Buy items using their web3 wallets.

5.2.1.4 Chat and FAQ

One of the key functionalities of the DAFNE+ platform is the FAQ section, which is designed to provide users with comprehensive information and support. Unlike traditional FAQ formats, the platform takes it a step

further by incorporating videos alongside the textual content. This innovative approach allows us to enhance user experience and engagement by offering visual explanations. The videos cover a range of topics, from basic concepts of cryptocurrencies like wallets, DAOs or NFTs, to tutorials on how to navigate and utilize different tools within our platform. By combining concise written explanations with dynamic visual demonstrations, the FAQ section ensures that users can easily grasp complex ideas and confidently utilize the features of the platform.

Another notable functionality of the DAFNE+ platform is the integration of Discord as the primary chat system. Instead of developing a chat interface from scratch, Discord's existing platform is going to be integrated, bringing several advantages. By using Discord, the platform offers users a familiar and intuitive communication environment. Discord provides a range of beneficial features, including robust moderation tools, voice and video chat capabilities, extensive customization options, and a sizable user base. This integration streamlines real-time communication among users, encouraging community engagement and facilitating efficient collaboration. The decision to integrate Discord not only saves development time and resources but also ensures users enjoy a reliable and feature-rich chat experience within the DAFNE+ platform.

5.2.1.5 GIT Management

The GIT Management tool should support content creation and distribution offering specific features for:

- Keeping track of the media asset updates.
- Referencing the original items as well as all the available versions identified as specific commits or tags in the git repository.
- Allowing for easy identification of owners and contributors to the various versions.

The GIT Management tool will offer a set of APIs to be integrated with the Content Management tool, to provide all those features during the content management activities (creation, editing, distribution). It will give a common abstract view to access the metadata from GitHub and GitLab based instances. This tool will be based on open source libraries in order to manage requests from those platforms through their APIs. If the backend of the CMS is developed in Python, IRCAM will provide its python-repository module based on the PyGitHub and python-gitlab modules already used by the IRCAM Forum. If the backend is developed in JavaScript, a specific module will be developed on top of the GitBeaker and Octokit.js modules. In both cases, a common API will be provided so that the CMS can get the required metadata from the repositories to the CMS.

5.2.1.6 Tools UI

The Application Layer includes all the user interfaces of the end-user application as well as the user interfaces provided by the DAFNE+ platform toolset.

Some of the DAFNE+ platform toolset, which is described more in detail in 5.2.6, will be available through user interface. The Tools' UIs, whereby it's possible, should be compliant with the design and style of the overall DAFNE+ platform, in order to be aligned with all the other tools and applications of the platform.

5.2.1.7 Tools Catalogue

The Tools Catalogue represents the entry point for any content production tools provided by the DAFNE+ ecosystem (see Chapter 5.2.6 for additional details). The catalogue will offer the possibility to search around the list of toolsets of the DAFNE+ platform, both external and internal and access directly to them.

The catalogue will provide 3 types of software components:

1. software to download and run on the local machine
2. software to download or access from an external web site with a URL
3. web application to load and use directly into the web browser

In case 1. the tools and their metadata are provided by external APIs on which the DAFNE+ platform is connected (i.e. the IRCAM Forum). The authenticated user can download the software directly by clicking on a given button.

In case 2. the metadata are stored on the CMS itself. The authenticated user can access the website or repository of the tool by clicking on a given link.

In case 3. the tools' metadata are stored on the CMS itself. The authenticated user can access the web application by clicking on a given link. When the web app produces a generative and/or interactive piece, the result is played back directly from the detail page of the NFT.

5.2.2 Blockchain Realm

The DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm will consist of a blockchain-ready framework able to:

- make simple and fast the interaction with the blockchain networks (Polygon [1] and Ethereum [2])
- facilitate the deployment and integration of Smart Contracts
- provide APIs interface for blockchain core features (NFTs, Tokens, Smart Contracts methods, Monitoring)

The Blockchain Realm will be exploited by the Application Layer and in particular by the DAO Section, NFT Marketplace and Content Management for accessing the Smart Contracts features and interacting with the blockchain network.

5.2.2.1 Smart Contracts

The smart contracts will keep track of all the media asset interactions expected in the DAFNE+ use cases and applications, including the usage of tools and libraries, the creation or adaptation of a media content item and its provision to the decentralized platform on behalf of the creators, the access and download on behalf of the consumers. The smart contracts will also allow for fine-grained monitoring and management of these actions as well as their translation in cryptocurrency-based values.

At the moment three categories of smart contracts to be implemented and integrated in the DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm were identified:

- Smart Contracts for transaction logging and verification
- Smart Contracts for digital asset management and tokenization/monetization
- Smart Contracts for governance (DAOs)

In addition, specific smart contracts for Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) management will be implemented. NFT tools and services are described in the next section.

5.2.2.2 NFT tools and services

The NFT tools and services component will be responsible for handling the interactions with the blockchain networks. Most of the rest of the DAFNE+ components will need to communicate with this tool first to make transactions and read related blockchain information. It will implement the following functionalities:

- a) Interacting with the DAFNE+ Smart Contracts.
- b) Building blockchain transactions.
- c) Logging important information.
- d) API interface to export its functionalities to the other DAFNE+ tools.

The architecture of the tool will be analysed in D4.1.

5.2.3 Identity and Profile Management

Identity and access management provides control over user validation and resource access. This process, usually identified as IAM (Identity and Access Management) ensures that the right people, using a digital entity, access a specific digital resource at the right time and for the right reasons.

The **digital identity** is a unique representation of a user and is linked with the user account.

A **digital resource** can be any combination of applications and data (e.g., access to applications, data, APIs, etc).

There are two main mechanisms included in the identity and access management:

- **Authentication** is the verification of a digital identity. Someone authenticates themselves to prove that they are the user they claim to be.
- **Authorization** is the process of determining what resources a user can access.

The DAFNE+ Identity and Profile Management tool will provide the following capabilities:

- **Seamless signup and login.** Registration of new users will be allowed through User Interface. Login will be available both through UI and APIs (using username and password and obtaining secure tokens).
- **Role-based access control (RBAC)** – The DAFNE+ Identity Management tool will allow for the definition of user groups and roles, applying a role-based access control to the digital resources.

The identity and profiling Management tool will also setup and collect **User Profiles**.

User Profiling is the process of identifying, collecting and storing the key information to generate a structured User Profile and then visualizing the knowledge out of these findings. User profiling helps in personalising a system to work according to user.

The DAFNE+ Identity and Profile Management tool will collect the useful information from users and will make them available to the AI Recommendation Engine for content filtering and personalization.

5.2.3.1 AI Recommendation Engine

The AI recommendation engine will run as a service in the background and it will be responsible for filtering the content of the DAFNE+ platform in order to provide users with **better content personalization**. To achieve its aims, the AI recommendation engine will access the user profile to get information on the user's interests and preferences, as well as the stored metadata of the DAFNE+ content that will describe the

content in the form of tags. These tags will be automatically computed from the content analysis tool and manually processed by the owners of the content when they upload their work onto the DAFNE+ platform.

Then, the AI recommendation engine will automatically process these two types of information and recommend specific content, as well as content creation tools, to the user that may be of more interest to them. The AI recommendation engine will rely on a novel content-based AI algorithm that will provide personalized recommendations based on user profiles, similar user profiles and popular content. The output of the AI recommendation engine will be a set of tags and possibly content identifiers that will be used to populate the DAFNE+ platform of the user with the most desirable content. More information on the AI recommendation engine will be provided in deliverables D3.1 and D3.2 “Content production tools and recommendation engine” that will be delivered in months M15 and M33, respectively.

5.2.4 Integration Layer

The integration layer refers to a list of APIs and tools that will enable the connection of the novel DAFNE+ services and components to 3rd-party applications and services. The intended users will be external developers that have registered to the DAFNE+ platform and wish to use the tools and services in their own projects, as well as content creators wishing to advertise their DAFNE+ created artefacts in their preferred apps.

The purpose of the component is twofold:

- a) Create easily readable and well documented APIs that expose the functionalities of various DAFNE+ services such as the creative tools for art generation.
- b) Create tools to allow the connection and sharing of DAFNE+ content to popular external platforms and services, for example social media platforms.

The detailed description of the component and its functionalities will be described in D4.2.

5.2.5 Storage Layer

The DAFNE+ storage layer is able to manage the entire persistency of the DAFNE+ Platform. The main role of the storage layer is to ensure the persistency of the media assets and in particular of NFTs.

In addition, the storage layer will manage the persistency of the user data (user profiles and general information) and will support the git management tool with the Large File System integration.

Media Assets and NFTs: IPFS

For an NFT to be useful, not only does it need to have an immutable pointer to its data, but the data must be stored and accessible. An NFT’s reference to off-chain data can be anything written in code. Most commonly, an NFT contains an HTTP URL that points to a location of data somewhere on the internet. With HTTP URLs, there must be trust that the service provider remains uncompromised and that the content they serve is actually the content being searched for. Even though the token part of an NFT is on a blockchain, the asset is only as good as its weakest link. IPFS is one of the best choices for storing and addressing data for NFTs.

IPFS is a modular suite of protocols for organizing and transferring data, designed from the ground up with the principles of content addressing and peer-to-peer networking. Because IPFS is open-source, there are

multiple implementations of IPFS. While IPFS has more than one use case, its main use case is for publishing data (files, directories, websites, etc.) in a decentralised way[3].

The main characteristics of IPFS are [2]:

- **Resilience:** Data will always be available as long as even a single node hosts the data. This also makes it harder to censor.
- **Reliability:** As any change to the file itself will change the hashed address, there are fewer trust assumptions when navigating to an address. Users can always compute the hash themselves to verify authenticity. This also minimizes risk around version control.
- **Deduplication:** If some data forms part of multiple datasets, each dataset only needs to link to one version of the data. Consequently, nobody has to store the entire dataset as links can be used to pull sections of data from across the network.

IPFS can solve the NFTs HTTP link issue. In fact, it enables users to store and retrieve content based on a “fingerprint” of the content itself (a cryptographic hash called CID). By putting an IPFS CID in an NFT, that NFT directly references the data itself rather than an HTTP link.

IPFS itself is not data storage – it’s a layer on top of data storage. Anyone can ask for a CID and get the uniquely corresponding content back as long as someone is broadcasting it to the network.

Large File System

When the binary assets are contained in a git repository, it is strongly advised to enable the LFS feature provided by both GitHub and GitLab. It improves the UX during uploading and downloading big files. This option could be addressed to the users and especially the contributors as a recommendation. In order to work locally, the users should install Git-LFS before cloning the repository as explained in the documentation [5].

5.2.6 Content Production Tools

The DAFNE+ Content Production Tools can be grouped in two different types:

- **Platform tools,** which are completely integrated in the DAFNE+ Platform and made available through the DAFNE+ UI
- **External tools,** which are part of the DAFNE+ ecosystem but made available outside of the DAFNE+ platform and don’t use the DAFNE+ UI. The external tools can be accessed in different ways depending on the kind of tools.

The sections below report a high-level description of the tools, collected during the evaluation of the specifications of the architectural components. Additional details about the content production tools will be provided in D3.1

The Table 4 below represents the template used for collecting all the needed information.

Name of Tool:	<name of the tool>
Functionality	<free text providing a short description of the operation of this module/component. >

Input Connections & Interfaces	< the actor/components from which the component receives input (input dependencies) and mentions the available connection interfaces e.g. API, User Interface etc.>
Output Connections & Interfaces	< the actor/components to which the component sends the results (output dependencies) and mentions also the available interfaces e.g. API, User Interface etc.>
Software Requirements	< any software requirements related to the architectural element, e.g., Docker, Databases, Kafka, etc....>
Hardware Requirements	<describes what hardware requirements are of the module, gives specifications about the hardware requirements which are necessary for the best functionality of the component>
Status of the development of the component	< describes if the component is “already developed” or “partially developed” or “to be developed from scratch”.>
WP and Task	<specifies the related WP and Task>
Responsible	<specifies responsible partner and main contact person>

TABLE 4: TEMPLATE FOR TOOL DESCRIPTION

5.2.6.1 Platform Tools

Name of Tool:	WebPd
Functionality	<p>WebPd is a highly modular web audio programming toolkit inspired by Pure Data. It allows artists to take their Pure Data patches and run them in web pages, therefore enabling non-programmers (sound designers, musicians, etc.) to design live and interactive audio for the web. It provides experienced web programmers with a complete audio toolkit that is production-ready, and enables efficient audio synthesis and processing in the browser.</p> <p>It is proposed as a feature embedded in the DAFNE+ platform to allow real-time previewing of Pd patches that could be delivered as artistic works.</p>
Input Connections & Interfaces	WebPd takes a PureData patch file as an input and optionally some dynamical user inputs like event messages and audio streams. It is connected to the local Web Audio API to run specific codes into the dedicated AudioWorklets.

Output Connections & Interfaces	WebPd sends some raw audio streams to the browser thanks to the Web Audio API and as the result of the real-time execution of the given patch. A specific graphical tool allows to visualize the rendered patch into the window of the browser.
Software Requirements	Modern browser
Hardware Requirements	Computer or smartphone
Status of the development of the component	already developed, work in progress
WP and Task	WP3 – T3.1
Responsible	IRCAM

TABLE 5: DESCRIPTION OF WEBPD

Name of Tool:	3D human pose estimation tool
Functionality	The tool will allow the user to import a video of humans performing tasks and it will output the humans' 3D poses using a model-based approach.
Input Connections & Interfaces	Through an interface, the user will be able to import videos
Output Connections & Interfaces	Through an interface, the user will be able to export human poses in FBX format, ready to be imported as animated sequences in Unity, Maya, etc.
Software Requirements	Python and related libraries, PyTorch, Docker
Hardware Requirements	An advanced GPU card is required (At least 8GB VRAM)
Status of the development of the component	The tool will be developed from scratch
WP and Task	WP3 - T3.2
Responsible	CERTH

TABLE 6: DESCRIPTION OF 3D HUMAN POSE ESTIMATION TOOL

Name of Tool:	3D object reconstruction tool
Functionality	The tool will allow a user to import multiple images of an object and it will output the 3D reconstructed version of the object.
Input Connections & Interfaces	Through an interface, the user will be able to import images

Output Connections & Interfaces	Through an interface, the user will be able to export 3D objects in. STL format that is suitable for 3D printing and CAD applications and/or .OBJ format that is suitable for game engines.
Software Requirements	Python and related libraries, PyTorch, Docker
Hardware Requirements	An advanced GPU card is required (At least 8GB VRAM)
Status of the development of the component	The tool will be developed from scratch
WP and Task	WP3 - T3.2
Responsible	CERTH

TABLE 7: DESCRIPTION OF 3D OBJECT RECONSTRUCTION TOOL

Name of Tool:	Automatic Art Generator
Functionality	<p>A tool that creates digital art automatically, using AI, without human intervention. Specifically, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) will be utilized, which will be trained on a large dataset of existing art pieces. The AI models will be able to generate 3 different styles of art. The user will select one of the 3 different styles and then the tool will generate a new artwork. The goal of this tool is to create a unique and visually appealing art without the need for manual painting.</p> <p>List of operations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The user logins into DAFNE+ platform 2) Select the Automatic Art Generator tool 3) The user can select a desired style form 3 different styles from the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impressionist paintings of Landscapes • Portraits of people • Modern paintings 4) AI methods generates the artwork in cloud 5) Display the generated artworks in DAFNE+ platform 6) Option to save and download the output image 7) Option to wrap it to an NFT and list it to the marketplace
Input Connections & Interfaces	<p>The tool receives input from the actors:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) End User, which selects a desired style from 3 different styles

	<p>Model library (database) on server is used to store ready to use pretrained models by the user of the platform.</p> <p>Connection interfaces:</p> <p>The selection of the style by the user will be done using the User Interface of the DAFNE+ platform. Then, the appropriate trained model will be used to generate a new artwork on server.</p>
Output Connections & Interfaces	<p>The tool sends results to the actors</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) User: the generated new artwork is displayed in DAFNE+ platform. The user can save and/or download it. <p>Component:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Blockchain Service/Marketplace
Software Requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A database to store the trained models on server 2) Optional: Decentralized database to store the generated image (if the user wants to create an NFT) 3) Docker to perform the inference of the trained models 4) API for the communication of the tool services with the DAFNE+ platform
Hardware Requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) GPU for real time inference using GAN models 2) Large storage capacity to store the AI models and the generated artworks 3) High-speed memory 4) Strong processing power (CPU) to perform the complex calculations required for inference 5) High speed network connection to transfer the generated image from server/cloud to DAFNE+ platform
Status of the development of the component	to be developed from scratch
WP and Task	WP3 – Task 3.2
Responsible	Synelixis Solutions S.A.

TABLE 8: DESCRIPTION OF AUTOMATIC ART GENERATOR

Name of Tool:	Style Transfer
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Functionality	<p>A tool that uses Neural Networks (NN) to apply the artistic style from one image to a completely different one. The goal of style transfer is to keep the content of the input image intact while changing its style to match that of the style image. The output is the generated image is a blend of input and style image. Generally, the functionality of a style transfer tool using AI is to generate new images that look like a particular artist's style, based on the inputs it is given.</p> <p>List of operations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The user logins into DAFNE+ platform 2) Select the Style Transfer tool 3) Uploading of the input image 4) Pre-processing of the input image 5) The user can select a desired style at UI of DAFNE+ platform 6) AI methods generates the artwork in cloud 7) Display the generated artworks in DAFNE+ platform 8) Option to save and download the output image 9) Option to wrap it to a NFT and list it to the marketplace
Input Connections & Interfaces	<p>All these interactions will be done by the user interface of the platform. The tool receives input from the actors:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) End User, which uploads the input image and selects a desired style to transfer from a list of predefined ones <p>Model library (database) on server is used to store ready to use pretrained models by the user of the platform.</p> <p>Connection interfaces:</p> <p>The user uses the User Interface of the DAFNE+ platform to upload the image and to select style. Then, the appropriate trained model will be used to generate a new artwork on server.</p>
Output Connections & Interfaces	<p>The tool sends results to the actors</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) User: the generated new artwork is displayed in DAFNE+ platform. The user can save and/or download it

	Component:
	1) Blockchain Service/Marketplace
Software Requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A database to store the trained models and the generated artworks 2) Optional: Decentralized database to store the generated image (if the user wants to create an NFT) 3) Docker to perform the inference of the trained models 4) API for the communication of the tool services with the DAFNE+ platform
Hardware Requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) GPU for real time inference using AI models 2) Large storage capacity to store the AI models and the generated artworks 3) High-speed memory 4) Strong processing power (CPU) to perform the complex calculations required for image pre-processing and inference 5) High speed network connection to transfer the generated image from server to DAFNE+ platform
Status of the development of the component	to be developed from scratch
WP and Task	WP3 – Task 3.2
Responsible	Synelixis Solutions S.A.

TABLE 9: DESCRIPTION OF STYLE TRANSFER

Name of Tool:	Virtual avatar personalization tool
Functionality	The tool will allow a user to import a photo of their face that will then be added to the avatar. In addition, the user will be able to alter the avatar's body parameters and clothes.
Input Connections & Interfaces	Through a web-based interface, the user will be able to personalize their avatar and add photos.
Output Connections & Interfaces	The avatar can be exported as a file in JSON format and added to other applications
Software Requirements	Node.js

Hardware Requirements	Lightweight tool with no particular hardware requirements
Status of the development of the component	The tool is partially developed, modifications will be made in the context of the project
WP and Task	WP3 - T3.2
Responsible	CERTH

TABLE 10: DESCRIPTION OF VIRTUAL AVATAR PERSONALIZATION TOOL

Name of Tool:	NFT content analysis tool
Functionality	Retrieve information from an NFT, the NFT could be audio, a video, a GIF or an image.
Input Connections & Interfaces	An API that will receive the URL of a NFT in the Body of a http POST call.
Output Connections & Interfaces	The API will return list of tags once analysed audio, skeleton actions, face sentiment analysis, OCR and objects
Software Requirements	Docker
Hardware Requirements	GPU
Status of the development of the component	Work in progress
WP and Task	WP3 - T3.3
Responsible	UPM

TABLE 11: DESCRIPTION OF NFT CONTENT ANALYSIS TOOL

5.2.6.2 External Tools

Name of Tool:	CoMo Elements - CoMo.te apps - CoMo.te helpers
Functionality	Mobile webapp to create collectively sound-movement interaction.
Input Connections & Interfaces	CoMo.te is a smartphone application (iOS and Android) that allows for streaming motion data (accelerometer, gyroscope) from the smartphone to desktop applications using either the OSC protocol or Websockets. The network's setup is facilitated by the use of a QR code generated by the targeted remote application receiving the motion sensor data.
Output Connections & Interfaces	CoMo can be seen as a distributed and interactive machine learning system, using web technologies. It is based on a software ecosystem

	<p>developed at IRCAM-STMS, using XMM, soundworks, waves.js. The client side allows for recording gestures, recognition, and plays related sounds. The server side performs the training and stores the statistical models.</p> <p>The server also outputs the data using OSC (OpenSoundControl), which allows connecting the CoMo-Elements to Max, Pd, Processing, openFrameworks, etc. on the local server.</p>
Software Requirements	<p>CoMo.te apps - iOS and Android</p> <p>CoMo.te helpers - Javascript and Max/MSP utilities to create server applications</p>
Hardware Requirements	<p>iOS or android smartphone</p> <p>MacOS, windows or linux server</p> <p>Wifi router</p>
Status of the development of the component	fully functional
WP and Task	WP3 – T3.1
Responsible	IRCAM

TABLE 12: DESCRIPTION OF CoMo ELEMENTS - CoMo.te APPS - CoMo.te HELPERS

Name of Tool:	Dicy2
Functionality	<p>"Dicy2 for Max" is a package for Max implementing interactive agents using machine-learning to generate musical sequences that can be integrated into musical situations ranging from the production of structured material within a compositional process to the design of autonomous agents for improvised interaction.</p>
Input Connections & Interfaces	<p>Dicy2 uses machine learning to generate structured variety from musical source material. This basis material is used to train the dicy2.agent object, which uses machine learning techniques to create an internal map of temporal relationships within the basis material. The user then sends queries to the agent (called a Scenario), and Dicy2 returns segments of musical material in response. Using pattern recognition algorithms, it looks for a 'best match' between the Scenario and the material stored in the memory, taking into account both musical similarities and the temporal structure of the Memory. To do</p>

	<p>this, the original source material is segmented, and each segment is given a label. A segment can be a MIDI note, a segment of an audio file, or anything in your original material that can be readily divided. Segments are labelled by similarity: similar segments are labelled identically, and dicy2 builds its model based on these labels. This combination of segments and labels is known as a Memory.</p>
Output Connections & Interfaces	<p>Once the Memory is built, you can send Dicy2 sequences of these labels (called a Scenario), and it will return optimized content that constitutes the 'best match' for the label sequence. The content (which is output as a list) can then be sent to further patches for rendering. The illustration below presents a schematic of the Dicy2 workflow, showing the most common helper abstractions.</p>
Software Requirements	<p>Max 8.5 or higher Dependency "MuBu for Max" version 1.10.5 or higher</p>
Hardware Requirements	<p>Mac OS High Sierra (10.13) or greater</p>
Status of the development of the component	<p>V3.0 first release</p>
WP and Task	<p>WP3 – T3.1</p>
Responsible	<p>IRCAM</p>

TABLE 13: DESCRIPTION OF DICY2

Name of Tool:	RAVE and nn~
Functionality	<p>A max / PureData (PD) external for real-time AI audio processing. Official implementation of RAVE: A variational autoencoder for fast and high-quality neural audio synthesis.</p>
Input Connections & Interfaces	<p>Torch library for learning new models.</p>
Output Connections & Interfaces	<p>nn~ is a Max/PD external for real-time AI Audio Processing.</p>
Software Requirements	<p>Max 8.5 or higher, Pure Data 0.53-1</p>

	libtorch, ffmpeg for learning
Hardware Requirements	macOS, windows or linux computer
Status of the development of the component	fully functional
WP and Task	WP3 – T3.1
Responsible	IRCAM

TABLE 14: DESCRIPTION OF RAVE AND NN~

Name of Tool:	RAVEv2
Functionality	Improvement of the existing RAVE model for style transfer and audio compression, including faster and higher quality generation, customizable synthesis controls, improvement of the prior model to allow structured temporal exploration, continuation and cooperation with a musician.
Input Connections & Interfaces	Realtime interface (Max/MSP and PureData external, VST plugins). Depending on the application, inputs can be audio signals, custom controls, labels.
Output Connections & Interfaces	Realtime interface (Max/MSP and PureData external, VST plugins). Depending on the application, outputs can be audio signals, latent trajectories, or metrics about the current generation.
Software Requirements	Max or PureData (enough for artists, musicians), Python (required for pro users aiming at performing custom trainings)
Hardware Requirements	For generation: a fairly recent CPU or GPU. New Apple M1-2 chips are perfect for the task. For training: a powerful GPU or TPU cluster. Training can also be performed online using cloud services.
Status of the development of the component	Partially developed.
WP and Task	WP3 – T3.1
Responsible	IRCAM

TABLE 15: DESCRIPTION OF RAVEv2

Name of Tool:	Soundworks
Functionality	Primarily focused on music, soundworks aims at supporting rapid development of real-time distributed applications using JavaScript. It

	provides abstractions to hide the complexity of the network and to foster very rapid-prototyping and trial-and-error workflows that are typical in artistic practices.
Input Connections & Interfaces	Full-stack JavaScript framework for distributed WebAudio and multimedia applications. Soundworks follows a client / server architecture where the server is written using Node.js and clients can be either regular browser clients or Node.js clients running for example on a Raspberry Pi.
Output Connections & Interfaces	The core of the framework is very minimal and dedicated at handling: - Http(s) server and basic routing - WebSockets initialization - Processes initialization - Distributed state management. Soundworks can be extended with plugins to reuse common logic such as audio file loading, clock synchronisation, etc. Each plugin leaves in a separate repo for better modularity and to simplify version management.
Software Requirements	Node.js 16+ A modern browser (e.g. Chrome, Firefox)
Hardware Requirements	macOS, windows or linux computer
Status of the development of the component	supported, in development
WP and Task	WP3 – T3.1
Responsible	IRCAM

TABLE 16: DESCRIPTION OF SOUNDWORKS

Name of Tool:	Spat
Functionality	Spat is a software suite for spatialization of sound signals in real-time intended for musical creation, post production, and live performances.
Input Connections & Interfaces	Spat relies on an efficient signal-processing library programmed in C++ to provide state-of-the-art software technologies. The software bundle comes as a set of Max/MSP external objects (i.e. plugins that can be inserted into the Max/MSP environment). Spat contains more than 250 external objects, many abstraction patchers, help patches, tutorials, large HRTF database, etc. Spat objects are highly configurable and most of them support up to 250 input/output channels (in Max 6

	or 7) and up to 8192 input/output channels (in Max8). DSP objects are also compatible with Max8 MC (« multi-channel ») patchcords.
Output Connections & Interfaces	The processor receives sounds from instrumental or synthetic sources, adds spatialization effects in real-time, and outputs signals for reproduction on an electroacoustic system (loudspeakers or headphones).
Software Requirements	Spat Package runs in Max 8 for windows and for macOS
Hardware Requirements	Compatible with macOS 10.11+ x86_64 (Intel processors) and arm64 (Apple Silicon M1) Compatible with Windows 10+ x86_64 (Intel processors)
Status of the development of the component	V5.2.9 fully functional
WP and Task	WP3 – T3.1
Responsible	IRCAM

TABLE 17: DESCRIPTION OF SPAT

6 Conclusion

The DAFNE+ consortium adopted a co-creation approach for the design of the DAFNE+ platform. In this course, it organised a number of events in different countries with diverse audiences to “sense” their needs and collect user requirements. The questionnaires were filled by 82 different potential users and this effort was driven mainly by the use case partners of the consortium. This process validated the beliefs of the consortium and made the user’s needs more concrete.

The collected user requirements were carefully studied and translated to system requirements which have guided the design of the DAFNE+ platform architecture. This collaborative work was conducted by the technical partners, who took into consideration apart from the user and system requirements, the technologies that better serve DAFNE+ aims to specify at high level the components of the DAFNE+ platform. These mature high-level specifications will guide the development activities in WP3 and WP4. As the functionality desired by the user is already rich in nature, we have prioritised the user needs and the component development accordingly. This will allow us to focus on a rich (yet sub-) set of aspects of interest to the users in the first pilot round, which will give us the time to develop the richer and final version of the platform later on.

The architecture described in this deliverable will be revised based on the outcomes of the pilots and on the lessons that we will have learnt by M30.

7 References

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8 Appendix – DAFNE+ Questionnaire for requirement collection

The questions asked to the users appear in the following table. In the first column titled ID, the ID of the question used in the internal process for creating this questionnaire is included, only as evidence of this work. As already described in chapter 3, different partners contributed different sets of questions targeting different aspects of the DAFNE+ ecosystem. The question ID starts with Cx where C corresponds to the targeted aspect and Qy which corresponds to the numbering within set C. After preparing all the questions, we searched for overlaps which resulted in merging questions. For this reason, in some questions, multiple IDs are listed as this question was relevant to multiple aspects.

DAFNE+questionnaire		
ID	Question	Possible Answers
C0_Q1	Please, provide your email address if you are interested in receiving DAFNE+ news.	textfield
C3_Q6	What is your activity?	Artist
		Creator/Designer
		Technical operator
		Academic, teacher
		Engineer/developer
		Art lover, collector, curator
		Business
		Researcher
		Other (textfield)
C0_Q2	What is your level of professionalism?	Just curious
		Beginner
		Amateur
		Student
		Semi-professional
		Professional
		Expert

C5.2_Q1 C5.3_Q1	Where is your creative area of expertise?	Music
		Sound
		Performing Arts
		Media Arts
		Webart and webapp
		Installations
		Architecture
		Design
		Digital Fabrication
		Material Processing
		Craft
		None
		Other (textfield)
C0_Q3	DAFNE+ will propose a set of advanced creative tools available in its platform. What is the main feature you would be interested in?	Music/sound creative tools
		3D and image/video processing tools
		None
C2_Q1	What is your main activity?	Music composition
		Computer music design
		Sound engineer, sound design
		Multimedia production
		AR/VR game design
		Other performing arts
		Other (textfield)
C2_Q2	How many applications do you use for music/sound production? (except plugins)	1

		Around 5
		Around 10
		More than 10
C2_Q3	Which advanced features are you interested in to be available in the DAFNE+ platform?	Music generativity and improvisation
		Collective interaction, distributed audio/music devices
		Sound spatialisation
		Deep learning for sound synthesis/processing
		Other (textfield)
C2_Q4	What would be your preferred environment(s) for using them?	Max
		Pure Data
		Ableton Live
		Unity, Unreal
		Other (textfield)
C2_Q5	Are you interested in web audio based applications?	1-5 (like)
C0_Q4	Are you also interested in features for 3D and image/video processing tools?	Yes
		No
C6_Q1	Which tools do you use the most in your work?	textfield
C3_Q7	What kind of content are you creating, or would you like to create?	textfield
C3_Q8	How important are tools that enable the automatic creation of content?	1-5 (like)
C3_Q1	Prioritize the following technologies based on your interest in content production from the most interesting technology to the least interesting one.	Full customisation of a virtual avatar by importing one's face image and/or body shape
		Extraction of skeleton animation sequences and body model parameters from videos

		Automatic reconstruction of 3D models from multiple images
		Automatic generation of artworks and transformation of given images to artworks of a specific artistic style
C3_Q2	What avatar customization do you think is important?	Body
		Face
		Skin Tone
		Clothes
		Other (textfield)
C3_Q3	What type of motion sequences are you most interested in modelling?	Full Body
		Face
		Fingers
		Other (textfield)
C3_Q4	What types of models/assets would you like to transform to 3D?	textfield
C3_Q5	Which artistic styles are you interested to transform images to?	Impressionism
		Cubism
		Surrealism
		Expressionism
		Hyperrealism
		Other (textfield)
C0_Q5	Are you also interested in features for music/sound creative tools?	Yes
		No
C0_Q6	Two main kinds of digital assets for creative production will be managed in the DAFNE+ platform: - Components : technical bricks/libraries used for content	Create / Develop components

	<p>synthesis/processing/manipulation. They result from an engineering process.</p> <p>- Repositories : aggregates of components and different kinds of data used in a creative process and enabling to reproduce/perform the artifact</p> <p>What will be your activities with these assets :</p>	<p>Use and create with components</p> <p>Create repositories</p> <p>Maintain / update existing repositories</p> <p>Collect repositories / Buy technical setups for artworks</p> <p>Study / analyse repositories and related artworks/artifacts</p> <p>Other (textfield)</p>
C0_Q7	<p>What type of contract do you generally use in your business?</p>	<p>Self-employed entrepreneur, freelancer</p> <p>Academic grants, research projects, public funding...</p> <p>Employee, worker, company member</p> <p>Artistic commissions</p> <p>Copyright contracts</p> <p>Personal resources</p> <p>Other (textfield)</p>
C7_Q1, C7_Q2, C7_Q5, C5.2_Qx	<p>Please select your level of agreement with each statement.</p>	<p>I believe my creative industry is inclusive and diverse.</p> <p>Creative work is properly valued and fairly rewarded.</p> <p>It is easy to share my revenue with other creators that participated directly or indirectly on my work.</p> <p>It is normal to pay a right of use for a computer program dedicated to the performance of a work.</p> <p>When an artistic work is sold, it is normal to remunerate the author of a computer program that is necessary for producing it.</p>
C5.3_Q6, C6_Q5	<p>What platforms do you use to publish you creative work?</p>	<p>GitHub, Gitlab, Wikifactory or other open-source platforms</p> <p>Private repository, personal website</p> <p>Commercial platform</p> <p>Social Media platform</p>

		I do not publish my creative work.
		Other (textfield)
C5.3_Q7, C5.3_Q8, C5.3_Q9	Do you experience any deficit you when publishing your work with open-source licenses?	textfield
C5.3_Q6, C6_Q5	If you use a commercial/social media platform to publish your work, which one(s) you use?	textfield
C5.3_Q6, C6_Q6	What feature(s) is/are missing from your favourite publishing platform?	textfield
C5.1_Q9	What is most important to consider before selling your work online?	Fair and transparent pricing and payment
		Popularity of platform (e.g. how many people will see my work)
		Environmental impact of platform
		Protection from theft
		Ability to choose a suitable copyright agreement for your work (e.g. free not-for-profit use)
		Maker community engagement and management
		Quality of creative work on platform
		Aesthetic aspects of the platform
		Other (textfield)
C5_Q17	How do you exploit your components and repositories? What is your main source of income from your assets?	I sell them and release the rights
		I sell them as an outcome of a service
		I sell the rights of editing/enriching
		I sell it to 3rd-party for reproduction
		Other (textfield)
C7_Q10	What would you change about how the creative work is valued and rewarded in your industry?	textfield

C7_Q9	What are the most invisible or less rewarded tasks of your creative work?	textfield
C5.2_Qx, C5.3_Q11	Please mark all the statements you believe to be true.	I would be interested in a fair market of creative functions allowing the remuneration of authors having participated directly or indirectly in my income.
		I would be interested in distributing my components/repositories in a marketplace for creatives.
		I would be willing to invest in a decentralized platform for maintenance and backup of components/repositories allowing the reproduction of artistic works.
		I would be interested in supporting the creators by collecting rights on part of their work.
		I would consider fair to mention other third party components/repositories used in other repositories.
C5.3_Q12	How important is the sustainability of your artworks to you?	1-5 (like)
C5.3_Q14	Do you think that a decentralized platform/management allows a better/longer sustainability?	textfield
C5_Q10	How familiar are you with blockchain technologies?	Very familiar
		I have used blockchain, but not in great extend
		I have a notion of what they are but do not use them
		Not familiar
C5.2_Q9	Do you consider blockchains as a good way to ensure authorship of your components/repositories and why?	textfield
C5_Q11	How familiar are you with the concept of the NFTs?	I have a technical level knowledge of NFTs
		I have high-level knowledge of the concept
		I have created/bought NFTs
		I have only heard of the term
		I do not know what NFTs are
C5_Q9	If you buy or create NFTs which marketplace(s) do you use?	OpenSea
		Rarible

		Foundation
		Nifty Gateway
		I do not buy or create NFTs
		Other (textfield)
C8_Q07, C8_Q04, C8_Q08, C8_Q13, C8_Q09, C5.2_Qx	Please select your level of agreement with each statement.	I believe the NFT space allows access to more assets that help creators in their work.
		Every resale of an NFT should revert a small percentage of the resale price to the original creator.
		I think that NFTs could be an relevant way of monetizing my library / Patchwork.
		I feel like NFT trading platforms do a good job in verifying the originality and authenticity of minted copyrighted works, which is beneficial to the author / artist / creator.
		A creative work in the public domain can legally be minted and sold as an NFT
C8_Q10, C8_Q02, C7_Q7	Please select your level of agreement with each statement.	Licensing of an NFT is easy to understand (or: I am fully aware of my rights and their limitations).
		A good knowledge of copyright law is necessary to navigate the NFT space safely.
		I believe using NFTs and Blockchain can help creators to sell and share their creative content
C8_Q12	Which of the following rights do you expect to own when buying an NFT of an artwork?	a) Visualize the artwork in high quality
		b) Download the artwork
		c) Show the artwork to friends and family
		d) Share the artwork on social media
		e) Use the artwork as my profile Picture on social media
		f) Resell the artwork
		g) Commercialize the artwork (merchandising)
		h) Stop others from using my artwork

		i) Stop others from selling copies of my artwork without my authorization
C5_Q14	Are you member of a Distributed Autonomous Organisation (DAO)?	Yes
		No
		I'm not familiar with DAOs
C5_Q14	Please specify the DAO(s) you are a member of.	textfield
C0_Q7	The DAFNE+ platform will enable to manage, share, monetize digital contents for different creative communities. Which one are you mainly interested in?	Non professional content production
		Professional sound/music production
		Art, design, making, fashion
C5.1_Q1	What types of creative media do you usually produce?	Music and/or Sound
		Film and Video
		Photography
		Games art
		Design
		Digital fashion
		Other (textfield)
C5.1_Q2	Which 3 digital tools have you used the most in the last year to make your creative work?	textfield
C5.1_Q3	Which platforms do you use to publish your digital media?	textfield
C5.1_Q4	What is the best feature of your favorite publishing platform?	textfield
C5.1_Q5	What feature is missing from your favourite publishing platform?	textfield
C5.1_Q6	Do you collaborate with others on creative media projects?	Yes
		No
C5.1_Q6	Which tools/platforms do you use to collaborate?	textfield
C5.1_Q7	What is most important when collaborating with others on creative media projects?	I can communicate easily with others to discuss the project

		It is easy for everyone to view, add to and edit work wherever they are
		It is clear who has worked on which aspects of the project
		That we have powerful editing software that can add to the quality of work
		It is easy to publish the work we produce collectively
		That the he payment of the participants be made automatically from an initial agreement
C5.1_Q10	What are the elements concerning the platform and the creative tools that you would like to see on the DAFNE+ platform?	textfield
C0_Q8	Would you also be interested in any of the following artistic uses?	Professional sound/music production
		Art, design, making, fashion
		No
C5.2_Q1	How do you define yourself as a component/repository creator?	Composer
		Sound designer, computer music designer
		Sound engineer
		Academic, teacher, researcher
		Engineer, developer
		Non professional creative, student
		N.A. - I don't produce components/repositories
C5.2_Q2	What is generally the purpose of the components/repositories you produce?	For my own artistic production
		Distributing tools to artists and creatives
		Assisting artists in a team-based production work
		Performing works
		Supporting courses with students
		Configuring studios or musical set-ups
		N.A. - I don't produce components/repositories
		Other (textfield)
C5.2_Q3	What are the main features of your flagship components/repositories? Please give an example on how you would use these assets.	textfield

C5.2_Q4	What do your components/repositories include?	Scripts, codes, patches
		Executables, plugins, DAWs sessions
		Media, sound, video
		Datasets, AI-models
		Documentation, tech rider
		Plans, drawings, schemes
		3D models and assets
		Other (textfield)
C5.2_Q5	Do you work as a team for the production of components/repositories?	Alone
		Collectively
		Iteratively (one person after the other)
		Other (textfield)
C5.2_Q6	Do you use a versioning tool to organize your components/repositories, which one and why?	textfield
C5.2_Q7	Documentation: Is it important to you that others are able to understand and use your components/repositories and why?	textfield
C5.2_Q8	Do you consider repository maintenance/versioning/update a necessary activity in the creative process and why?	textfield
C0_Q9	Would you also be interested in any of the following artistic uses?	Non professional content production
		Art, design, making, fashion
		No
C5.3_Q2	How do you define yourself as a "repository/component creator" ?	Maker
		Designer
		Engineer
		Artist
		Creator

		Other (textfield)
C5.3_Q3	Which are your main activities?	Prototyping
		3D modeling
		Coding
		Making
		Documenting
		Communications (SoMe)
		Business Development
		Other (textfield)
		C5.3_Q4
No		
Other (textfield)		
C5.3_Q5	What does your repository include?	CAD, OBJ, STL, STEP, .3MF,..
		GCODE
		PNG, JPG, DRW, DXF
		Code (Python, XTML, ...)
		Markdown file, txt, pdf
		Other (textfield)
C5.3_Q10	Do you consider versioning as a necessary activity in the creative process and why?	textfield
C0_Q10	Would you also be interested in any of the following artistic uses?	Non professional content production
		Professional sound/music production
		No
C1_Q2	How do you expect to interact with the DAFNE+ platform?	Using a browser web app
		Using mobile app

		Integrate it with other existing systems via APIs
		Install it on my laptop
		Other (textfield)
C5_Q7	Which abilities would you consider of value?	Directly importing artefacts created on DAFNE+ to 3rd-party software
		Using widgets of DAFNE+ content
		Sharing DAFNE+ content on social media
		Other (textfield)
C1_Q4	Please rank these aspects from the most important to the least important to you about the DAFNE+ Platform	Security
		User Experience
		Performance
		Contents
		Cross-platform usage
C1_Q1	How familiar are you with cloud architecture?	0-10
C1_Q3	What kind of authentication mechanisms are you familiar with?	Username and Password
		Authentication Token
		Two factor authentication
		3rd party authentication (e.g., Facebook, Google, etc...)
C4_Q1	How important is for you to get personalized content recommendations on the DAFNE+ platform?	0-10
C4_Q2	Based on what criteria do you want the personalisation of the content of the DAFNE+ platform to be performed?	User profile
		Preferences of similar users
		Popular content

		Other (textfield)
C4_Q3	How important is for you to manually correct keywords recommended by the DAFNE+ content analysis algorithm?	0-10
C5_Q15	Are you the owner of a Web3 wallet?	Yes
		No
C5_Q15	Please state which wallets you own. (e.g. Metamask, Coinbase... etc)	textfield
C5_Q12	Which blockchain networks have you used before?	Ethereum
		Polygon
		Solana
		Cardano
		Ripple
		None
		Other (textfield)
C5_Q5	How much information would you like to be provided with about the transactions and operations performed on the network level?	0-5
C5_Q6	Prioritize the following parameters for the DAFNE+ blockchain functionality	Performance/Transactions speed
		Transaction cost
		Level of decentralization
		Interoperability with other blockchains
		Using open-source networks and solutions
		Compatibility with major external NFT marketplaces
		Community/Users size

		Energy consumption
		Security
C5_Q7	Which features would you like the NFTs to include?	Being time-limited
		Being non-hashable
		Ability to be upgraded
		Indifferent/irrelevant to me
		Other (textfield)
C6_Q2	Which elements would you value in APIs giving access to the DAFNE+ platform features?	Readability
		Documentation
		UI Appearance
		Being open-source
		Friendliness to use
		Indifferent/ irrelevant to me
		Other (textfield)
C6_Q4	Which API Documentation tools are you most familiar with?	Swagger
		Postman
		apiDocs
		Redocly
		None
		Other (textfield)

